

Figure 5: NKG2A-edited primary NK and NK-92 cells act synergistically with RIG-I stimulation to promote anti-tumor toxicity.

Primary NK cells were electroporated with RNPs containing two gRNA targeting NKG2A (NKG2Ag) or a control gRNA (-CTRg) and kept in culture for at least one week before assessing *in vitro* cytotoxicity in combination with target-cell RIG-I stimulation. Target cells were stimulated 24 h before cocultures with 0.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA). (a) Specific lysis from primary NK cells is presented at different E:T ratios on Caco-2 ($n=7$ donors, mean \pm SD) and EFO-21 cells ($n=5$ donors, mean \pm SD). (b) The observed contribution to NK-cytotoxicity was calculated for the E:T ratio 2.5:1 as average for: NKG2A deletion (3p-ssRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTRg NK), RIG-I stimulation (3p-dsRNA -CTRg NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTRg NK), and potential synergy in combination ((3p-dsRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTRg NK) - (3p-ssRNA NKG2Ag NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTRg NK) - (3p-dsRNA -CTRg NK - 3p-ssRNA -CTRg NK)) normalized to 100% of the increase (divided by the addition of all positive effects). (c, d) Specific lysis of Caco-2 and EFO-21 cells by NKG2A-edited NK-92 cells (c, $n\geq 3$ independent experiments) and observed contribution to NK cytotoxicity calculated as explained in b (d). (e-h) Primary intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma (Liver CCC) derived organoids were characterized by immunohistochemistry against Cytokeratin 7 and CA19-9 (e) and used as model to measure NK-cytotoxicity. The organoids were treated with 0.4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ RIG-I ligand (3p-dsRNA) or control RNA (3p-ssRNA) for 24 h and cocultured with -CTRg and NKG2Ag electroporated NK cells for 24 h. Flow cytometry measurements of NKG2A on NK cells and HLA-E on target cells (f), and specific lysis (g, $n=4$ donors, mean \pm SD) are shown. The contribution of RIG-I stimulation, NKG2A deletion, and the combination was calculated for E:T ratio 2.5:1 (h). Statistical comparisons were performed using two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šidák's post-hoc test (a, c, g), or paired t test for surface expression of NKG2A and HLA-E (f). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.005$, **** $p < 0.001$.